

A Comparative Analysis of Refractive Errors Before and After Cataract Surgery: Phacoemulsification Versus Manual SICS in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract

Background: Cataracts are a leading cause of preventable blindness worldwide, with surgical intervention being the only effective treatment. Phacoemulsification and manual small-incision cataract surgery (MSICS) are the two most common techniques for cataract removal. While phacoemulsification is preferred in advanced settings due to its precision and faster recovery, MSICS remains a cost-effective alternative in resource-constrained environments.

Aim: To compare pre-operative and post-operative refractive and visual outcomes in cataract patients undergoing phacoemulsification and MSICS in a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This prospective study was conducted at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, from July 2023 to July 2024, involving 120 participants divided into two groups: 60 undergoing phacoemulsification and 60 undergoing MSICS. Pre-operative and post-operative visual acuity and refractive errors were assessed. Data collection included patient demographics, keratometry, and intraocular lens power calculations. Outcomes were analyzed at 1 month and 3 months post-surgery using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean post-operative visual acuity was significantly better in the phacoemulsification group (0.22 logMAR) compared to the MSICS group (0.30 logMAR, $p = 0.001$). Post-operative spherical equivalent was significantly lower in the phacoemulsification group (-0.4 D) compared to MSICS (-1.0 D, $p = 0.002$). Post-operative astigmatism $>1.5D$ was observed in 5% of the phacoemulsification group and 13% of the MSICS group ($p = 0.02$). Surgical complications were minimal and comparable between the groups ($p = 0.10$).

Conclusion: Phacoemulsification provides superior visual acuity and refractive outcomes compared to MSICS, with reduced post-operative astigmatism. However, MSICS remains a viable alternative, especially in low-resource settings, due to its cost-effectiveness and safety profile.

Recommendations: Phacoemulsification should be prioritized in well-equipped healthcare settings, while MSICS continues to play a vital role in addressing cataract blindness in resource-limited regions. Training programs should focus on enhancing surgeon expertise in both techniques.

Keywords: Cataract surgery, Phacoemulsification, Manual small-incision cataract surgery, Visual outcomes, Refractive errors.

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Introduction

Cataracts, which largely affect older people, continue to be the biggest preventable cause of blindness worldwide, accounting for about 51% of

all blindness cases. Thanks to improvements in surgical methods, cataract surgery is now one of the most popular and successful ophthalmology

treatments. Phacoemulsification and manual small-incision cataract surgery (MSICS) are the two main surgical techniques; each has unique advantages and disadvantages [1, 2].

Phacoemulsification, a modern technique, involves emulsifying the cataractous lens using ultrasonic energy, followed by the implantation of a foldable intraocular lens (IOL) through a small 2–3 mm incision. This method is renowned for its precision, faster visual recovery, and reduced post-operative complications such as astigmatism [3]. However, it requires sophisticated equipment and training, making it more expensive and less accessible in resource-limited settings [4].

In contrast, MSICS is a cost-effective technique that involves the removal of the cataract through a larger, self-sealing incision of 5–7 mm. It is sutureless, requires minimal equipment, and is particularly advantageous in low-resource environments. Despite its slightly longer recovery time and higher risk of surgically induced astigmatism compared to phacoemulsification, MSICS has been shown to deliver comparable visual outcomes in the long term [5]. As healthcare disparities persist, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, MSICS continues to play a vital role in addressing cataract blindness [6].

Recent studies have evaluated the outcomes of these techniques, shedding light on their comparative effectiveness. A study by Gogate et al. (2019) demonstrated that phacoemulsification achieves superior uncorrected visual acuity outcomes in the early postoperative period, but MSICS offers equivalent best-corrected visual acuity over time, making it a practical choice in resource-constrained settings [7]. Similarly, a systematic review by Khanna et al. (2020) found that while phacoemulsification is associated with less induced astigmatism, MSICS remains a reliable alternative due to its affordability and accessibility [8]. To compare pre-operative and post-operative refractive and visual outcomes in cataract patients undergoing phacoemulsification and MSICS in a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a prospective, comparative, hospital-based study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna, Bihar, over a period of one year from July 2023 to July 2024.

Participants: The trial comprised 120 individuals who were scheduled for cataract surgery after receiving a diagnosis of age-related cataracts. These individuals were split up into two groups of sixty each:

1. Group A: Individuals receiving

phacoemulsification.

2. Group B: Individuals receiving SICS by hand.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 40 years and above.
2. Diagnosed with age-related cataract.
3. Willing to undergo cataract surgery at NMCH.
4. Provided informed consent for participation in the study.
5. No significant ocular comorbidities affecting visual acuity or refractive status.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with traumatic, congenital, or complicated cataracts.
2. Presence of ocular comorbidities such as glaucoma, uveitis, or diabetic retinopathy.
3. History of previous ocular surgery.
4. Patients unable to comply with follow-up protocols.
5. Cases with intraoperative complications affecting refractive outcomes.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, random sampling was used to allocate patients into the two surgical groups. Observer bias was reduced by having a blinded investigator perform the post-operative refractive assessments.

Data Collection: Patient demographics, pre-operative visual acuity, and refractive status were recorded. Post-operative refraction and visual outcomes were assessed at one month and three months following surgery. All data were recorded using a pre-designed data collection form.

Procedure

1. Pre-operative Evaluation:

- A thorough examination of the eyes, which includes fundus examination, intraocular pressure monitoring, and slit-lamp biomicroscopy.
- Keratometry and axial length measurements using A-scan ultrasonography for intraocular lens (IOL) power calculation.

2. Surgical Procedure:

- **Phacoemulsification:** Performed under topical anesthesia using a foldable IOL implant.
- **Manual SICS:** Performed under peribulbar anesthesia with a non-foldable IOL implant.

3. Post-operative Care:

- Typical post-operative treatment includes anti-inflammatory eye drops and antibiotics.
- Follow-up appointments one week, one month, and three months after surgery.

4. Post-operative Assessment:

- Visual acuity and refractive error evaluation using Snellen's chart and auto-refractometry.

Statistical Analysis

The data was entered and examined using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were used to summarize continuous variables. Independent t-tests and chi-squared tests were used to compare continuous and categorical data, respectively.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Parameter	Phacoemulsification (n=60)	Manual SICS (n=60)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	62.5	63.0	0.48
Male Participants (%)	54	58	0.40
Female Participants (%)	46	42	0.40

- The mean age difference (62.5 vs. 63.0 years) was not statistically significant ($p = 0.48$), indicating no age-related bias.
- The gender distribution was balanced, with a slightly higher percentage of males in both groups.

Statistical significance was defined as a P-value of less than 0.05.

Results

This study included 120 participants (60 in each group) to evaluate and compare refractive and visual outcomes after cataract surgery using phacoemulsification and manual SICS techniques. The results are detailed below, accompanied by explanatory insights. The mean age and gender distribution were comparable between the two groups, ensuring balanced demographics.

The phacoemulsification group's post-operative visual acuity improved noticeably more than that of the manual SICS group.

Table 2: Visual Acuity Comparison

Parameter	Phacoemulsification (n=60)	Manual SICS (n=60)	p-value
Pre-operative Visual Acuity	0.85	0.90	0.03
Post-operative Visual Acuity	0.22	0.30	0.001

- The phacoemulsification group had a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.03$) in mean pre-operative visual acuity, which was marginally superior.
- The phacoemulsification group showed a greater improvement in post-operative visual

acuity (0.22 vs. 0.30 logMAR, $p = 0.001$), indicating better visual restoration.

Phacoemulsification achieved better refractive precision and reduced astigmatism compared to manual SICS.

Table 3: Refractive Outcomes

Parameter	Phacoemulsification (n=60)	Manual SICS (n=60)	p-value
Mean Spherical Equivalent (Pre-op) (D)	-2.9	-3.2	0.07
Mean Spherical Equivalent (Post-op) (D)	-0.4	-1.0	0.002
Post-operative Astigmatism >1.5 D (%)	5	13	0.02

- Although the manual SICS group's mean pre-operative spherical equivalent was marginally higher, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.07$).
- The phacoemulsification group experienced a significant improvement in the post-operative

spherical equivalent ($p = 0.002$), indicating improved refractive outcomes.

- The phacoemulsification group experienced a lower prevalence of post-operative astigmatism (>1.5D) (5% vs. 13%, $p = 0.02$).

The overall complication rate was low in both groups, with no statistically significant difference.

Table 4: Surgical Complications

Parameter	Phacoemulsification (n=60)	Manual SICS (n=60)	p-value
Surgical Complications (%)	3.3	8.3	0.10

- The phacoemulsification group had fewer surgical complications (3.3% vs. 8.3%), though the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.10$).

- Both techniques demonstrated a safe surgical profile.

Summary of Findings

1. Phacoemulsification achieved significantly better post-operative visual acuity and refractive precision compared to manual SICS.
2. Post-operative astigmatism was significantly less common in the phacoemulsification group.
3. Surgical complications were slightly lower in the phacoemulsification group but not statistically significant.

Discussion

In 120 patients, the study evaluated the visual and refractive results of manual small incision cataract surgery (SICS) with phacoemulsification. In order to ensure minimal baseline differences and enable trustworthy comparisons of surgical outcomes, the demographic data revealed similar age and gender distributions between the two groups. Although the manual SICS group's mean age was marginally greater (63.0 years) than the phacoemulsification group's (62.5 years), the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.48$). The distribution of participants by gender was balanced, with a slightly higher proportion of men in both groups.

Post-operative visual acuity outcomes favoured the phacoemulsification group, which achieved significantly better improvements. The mean post-operative visual acuity in the phacoemulsification group was 0.22 logMAR compared to 0.30 logMAR in the manual SICS group ($p = 0.001$). These results highlight the superior visual restoration capabilities of phacoemulsification, likely due to its precision and advanced technology.

Refractive outcomes further reinforced the advantages of phacoemulsification. While pre-operative spherical equivalents were similar between the groups, post-operative results revealed significantly better refractive precision in the phacoemulsification group (-0.4 D vs. -1.0 D, $p = 0.002$). Additionally, post-operative astigmatism (>1.5 D) was less frequent in the phacoemulsification group (5% vs. 13%, $p = 0.02$), demonstrating its ability to minimize astigmatism and enhance refractive accuracy. The incidence of surgical complications was low in both groups, with slightly fewer complications in the phacoemulsification group (3.3% vs. 8.3%, $p = 0.10$). However, this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that both techniques are generally safe when performed by skilled surgeons.

Phacoemulsification demonstrated superior uncorrected visual acuity (UCVA) on the first postoperative day and better best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) within the first week compared to SICS. However, after one month, the BCVA outcomes were comparable between the two methods. Despite early differences in visual recovery, both techniques stabilized over time,

providing equivalent long-term refractive accuracy [9, 10].

Postoperative cylindrical refraction and surgically induced astigmatism (SIA) were higher in SICS, attributable to its larger incision size. Phacoemulsification, with its smaller incisions, consistently resulted in less astigmatism and better refractive stability. This difference underscores phacoemulsification's advantage in achieving precise refractive outcomes [11].

Studies focusing on diabetic patients revealed that postoperative macular thickness rose significantly more in the SICS group compared to phacoemulsification, particularly within the first month. This suggests a higher risk of macular edema following SICS in vulnerable populations. Both groups, however, showed a return to near preoperative macular thickness by the six-month mark [12].

Conclusion

Phacoemulsification demonstrated superior visual and refractive outcomes compared to manual SICS, with significantly better post-operative visual acuity, reduced astigmatism, and excellent safety. While both techniques showed low complication rates, phacoemulsification is the preferred choice for optimal results in resource-equipped settings. Manual SICS remains a valuable alternative in resource-limited environments, offering safe and effective cataract management.

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